

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

APPROPRIATION ACTIVITIES IN SPEAKING: PRACTICED CONTROL, DRILLINGS AND CHANTS

Hasanova A.

ORCID: 0009-0003-2916-7541

Islamli A.

ORCID: 0009-0002-1535-7873

Azerbaijan National Aviation Academy

ABSTRACT

In some of our Institutions the English language is teach as the second language. In that case the teachers comprise the methods and principles in order to enable student learning. These specific strategies are determined partly on subject matter to be taught and partly by the nature of the learner. In this article the authors show the teachers how to teach speaking to the learners. They try to explain the easy ways of teaching speaking, giving them appropriation activities, which include writing tasks, reading aloud, drilling and chants.

Keywords: fluency, drillings, general rule, milling activities, chants.

Introduction

“English is a global language.” A headline of this kind must have appeared in a thousand newspapers and magazines in recent years. “English rules” is an actual example, presenting to the world an uncomplicated scenario suggesting the universality of the languages spread and the likelihood of its continuation. A language achieves a genuinely global status when it develops a special role that is recognized in every country. This might seem like stating the obvious, but it is not, for the notion of “special role” has many facets. Such a role will be most evident in countries where large numbers of the people speak the language. In many countries, however, lack of government support, or shortage of foreign aid has hindered the achievement of language-teaching goals. Distinction such as “first”, “second” and “foreign” language status are useful, but we must be careful not to give them a simplistic interpretation. In particular, it is important to avoid interpreting the distinction between “second” and ‘foreign” use as difference in fluency or ability. Although we might expect people from a country where English has some a sort of official status to be more competent in the language than those where it has none, simply on grounds if greater exposure, it turns out that this is not always so.

Main body

The term appropriation, rather than either controlled practice or restructuring, is used for the second stage because it captures better the sense that learning a skill is not simply a behavior (like practice) or a mental process (like restructuring), but one of the collaborative construction. Over time, and through social interaction, the skill, which is first “other-regulated”, becomes “self-regulated”. Central to the notion of a transfer of control is the idea that aspects of the skill are appropriated. Appropriation has connotations of taking over the ownership of something, of “making something ones own”.

In fact, rather than talk of controlled practice, it may be more helpful to talk about practiced control. Controlled practice is repetitive practice of language items in conditions where the possibility of making mistakes is minimized. Typically this takes the form of drilling. Practiced control, on the other hand, involves demonstrating progressive control of a skill where the possibility of making mistakes is ever-present, but where support is always at hand. To use the analogy of learning to ride a bicycle, it is like being allowed to pedal freely, but with someone running along right behind, just in case. In practiced control, control (or self-regulation) is the objective of the practice, whereas in controlled practice, control is simply the condition under which practice takes place.

Drillings and Chants

Gaining control of the speaking skill involves practicing that control. But the notion of practiced control need not rule out of the value of some mechanical and repetitive practice activities of the type traditionally associated with drilling. Drilling-that is imitating and repeating words, phrases, and even whole utterances - may in fact be a useful noticing technique, since it draws attention to material that learners might not otherwise have registered. Thus, after learners have listened a taped dialogue, and studied the transcripts, the teacher can isolate specific phrases or utterances and ask learners to repeat them.

Another argument often used in favour of drilling is that it provides a means of gaining articulatory control over language- of “getting your tongue round it”. This is probably more useful when learners are already familiar with an item – when they have already “got their minds round it”- but are still having trouble producing the item fluidly. That is to say, drilling acts as a kind of tuning for articulation, rather than as a learning technique in itself. This is likely to be particularly useful in gaining control of short, functional chunks and their associated intonation patterns, such as these dis-course markers:

By the way	That reminds me	As I was saying
While I remember	Before I forget	Talking on which

Or these sentence starters:

Do you mind if I...?	The thing is, ...	Do you happen to know...?
Do you think you could...?	Would it be Ok if I...?	

Or social formulas and useful expressions:

How do you do?	See you later	Just looking, thanks.
Can I take a message?	How do you spell that?	

Or catchphrases and idiomatic phrases:

Better late than never	Long time no see	Look who is talking
It is on the tip of my tongue	The sooner the better	

By both memorizing these chunks gaining control over their fluent articulation, learners are increasing their fluency store. As we see fluency is the capacity to string long runs together, with appropriately placed pausing. This in turn is partly a function having a store of memorized phrases, or chunks, that act as “islands of reliability”, on which the speaker can momentarily rest while planning the next run. Drilling may help in the storing and in the retrieving of these chunks as whole units. In this sense, drilling, in effect, is aimed primarily at developing accuracy.

As a general rule of thumb, drilling involves quick choral i.e. (all the class) repetition of the teachers model (or a recorded model on tape), followed by individuals randomly nominated by the teacher. It is important that the learners mimic the stress and information of the model: there is a world of difference between How do you spell that and How do you spell that, for example.

For the phrases with “empty slots”, such as sentence starts, the teacher can provide prompts to fill the slot. For example:

<p>Teacher: Do you mind if I sit here? Student 1: Do you mind if I sit here? Teacher: Smoke Student 2: Do you mind if I smoke? Teacher: Open the window Student 3: Do you mind if I open the window? etc.</p>
--

Here, then, are some techniques that involve either individual or choral repetition:

Drilling –the learners are played a recording of an interaction, in which are embedded a number of useful chunk-type items, such as formulaic ways of expressing specific speech acts. After working on their understanding of the dialogue, they are given the transcript. The

recording is played again, but the teacher pauses it at strategic points, and the learners repeat the immediately preceding utterance in unison, and then individually. Only key phrases are repeated, not the whole dialogue. Here, for example, is how part of the above mentioned dialogue might be used:

Recording	Students
A: Hey, Barry, what a great tie! B: Thanks. Actually, I have had it for ages, but I have never wear it.	
A: It suits you. {pause}	(chorus) It suits you. (individual 1) It suits you. (individual 2) It suits you. (individual 3) It suits you.
Listen, Barry. I was thinking, do you fancy lunch together some time this week?	
B: That would be nice.{pause}	(chorus) That would be nice. (individual 1) That would be nice (individual 2) That would be nice (individual 3) That would be nice.
What about Friday? A: Perfect. Do you mind if I ask Jackie? B: Well, actually, I am sorry AI.	
I would rather, you did not. {pause}	(chorus) I would rather you did not. (individual 1) I would rather you did not. (individual 2) I would rather you did not. (individual 3) I would rather you did not.
Etc.	

As further reinforcement, learners could be asked to underline the drilled segments on the transcript and to mark the main stressed words in each segment. They can then read the dialogues aloud, paying special attention to the underlined sections.

Chants – a more playful form of practice that replicates the repeating and chunking nature of drilling is the use of chants. And because they are contextualized, the chunks in chants may in fact be more memorable

A funny thing happened...
What happened?
A funny thing happened to Lee.
It is funny how things like that happen.
The same thing happens to me.
An awful thing happened...
What happened?
An awful thing happened to Jim.
It is awful how things like that happen.
The same thing happened to him.

Having heard it a few times, learners can attempt to reconstruct it in written form, before chanting it in unison. If there is a dialogic element, as in the above chant, the class can be divided in two, each half taking alternate lines. The chanting should be relatively fast, regular, and rhythmic. (Asking learners to mark the main stressed words helps) Then they can try substituting elements to produce new “verses”, using prompts, such as:

Scary...Gus...us creepy...fleur...her...
crazy...Clem...them

Writing tasks

It may seem strange to have a section on writing in a book that is about speaking. But writing has a useful role to play as an initial stage in the appropriation of newly encountered language to using. Inevitably, because of the constraints placed on mental processing by the demands of real-time speaking, learners tend to rely on a very narrow repertoire of memorized expressions in face-to-face interaction. So, an important function of classroom speaking activities is to help learners extend their range of such features. To do this, it may sometimes help to reduce the processing demands placed on them in order to give them time to consciously access alternatives to their habitual repertoire. One way of “slowing down” processing is to turn the speaking task into a writing one. Here are some ways of doing that;

Dictation, paper conversations, computer-mediated chat, rewriting and so on.

Conclusion

In this article we have looked at some ways that Learners may achieve greater control over their own speaking through classroom processes of appropriation. Activities aimed at appropriation provide learners with

than in standard drills. After all, many learners are familiar with catchphrases and idiomatic one-liners from having picked them up listening to pop songs or playing computer games. To work best, the chants should incorporate repeated examples of short, multi-word sequences, and should have a consistent rhythm. It helps if the chants have been prerecorded. Here, for example, is a chant that embeds a number of narrating expressions:

a supportive framework in which they can practice control. The support may take the form of:

- A model, which is repeated, as in drills or chants.
- A writing task, which allows longer processing time than does “live” speaking
- Reading aloud from a text

We have now looked at two of the stages of our three-stage model of skills development awareness and appropriation and in our future works we are going to discuss the other models of skill development.

References

1. Cameron, D (2001) Working with Spoken Discourse
2. Sage Publications, Carter R, and McCarthy M, (1997) Exploring Spoken English, Cambridge University Press.
3. Minavvar Firudin Mammadova, Banovsha Mammadova, Gunel Vilayat Bayramova, Tamilla Ahmedzade “Acquisition of Language, Linguistics Via Computer (AI) in Higher Education Institutions and its Effects” 2025, Forum for Linguistic studies, 466-480
4. Mammadova Minavvar Firudin “The ways of teaching vocabulary to the cadets in the Military Institute,” Science of Europe, 109, 35-38 ,2023
5. Mammadova Minavvar Firudin, Novruzova Zamina “Teaching approaches to the EL reading in the Military Institute” Science of Europe 111, 19-21,2023
6. Mammadova M.F. “Principles of Language learning in Higher Military School” 2021, Problems of Linguistic p. 80-86
7. Minavvar Mammadova Firudin International e-journal of Educational Studies 10(26) 55-64, 2018 “Effective test-taking strategies for the Higher Military School”